

Supplementary Material

The appendix contains further elements illustrating the methodological approach as described in the article. As pointed out in the article, the ecosystem approach and the proposed framework are particularly useful to lead the digital transformation in areas where data and information systems play an important role. At the difference of frameworks that focus on ecosystems around national data portals, the proposed analytical framework is geared towards the development of thematic data ecosystems at an international level. Thus, it can for example be used to analyse the current state of implementation of a digital ecosystem and guide the development of an action plan based on this initial analysis in direct collaboration with key stakeholders. To do so, we suggest to proceed iteratively – both as regards the delimitation of the ecosystem, its analysis, and the progressive involvement of additional stakeholders.

Fig. 1. The four cornerstones of good data ecosystem governance (with checklists)

Analysts may proceed according to the following step-by-step process:

1. Carry out desk research to identify the existing elements, the main purposes, and the key stakeholders of a given thematic ecosystem; provide an initial description of the ecosystem, addressing its four cornerstones: (i) data sharing; (ii) interoperability and shared infrastructures; (iii) stakeholder involvement; and (iv) economic sustainability. This can be done using the check lists provided in the article (fig. 1). Be careful to differentiate between areas where further ecosystem development is needed, and areas on which information is still lacking. Try filling in the knowledge gaps by talking to a few key informants familiar with the ecosystem or by carrying out a workshop among ecosystem participants.

Critical at this stage is the initial delimitation of the thematic ecosystem: If the ecosystem under consideration is too large (e.g. “environmental data ecosystem” versus “biodiversity data ecosystem”), it will require a comparatively larger effort to capture it as a whole and subsequently to lead its development; if it is too small (e.g. “biodiversity data ecosystem for the Republic of Ireland” vs. “global biodiversity data ecosystem”), important synergy potentials may be missed.

2. Carry out expert interviews with representatives of all key stakeholders of the ecosystem, using an adapted version of the questionnaire provided below (A1). For the purpose of the analysis, identify all the passages that address governance and/or coordination issues, and assign them to one or several of the categories provided in the check lists. If additional topics are salient in the interviews, add them as additional categories. Summarize the findings in a report.

The report may highlight the aspects that are in focus among the ecosystem

participants at a given point in time and point to possible gaps with regard to good ecosystem governance by comparing them to the status quo of the ecosystem and to the check lists.

3. Develop an action plan for the development of the digital ecosystem in direct cooperation with key stakeholders. Regularly track the progress of its implementation.

Iterate any of the three steps whenever deemed useful, triangulating between the different approaches of data collection.

A1. Interview Questionnaire Used for the Expert Interviews

In view of the creation of a Linked Open Data Ecosystem for the Performing Arts, [name of the institution] is interviewing key stakeholders to find out what their view is on issues related to the development of staff skills and organizational capacities. Furthermore, we are interested in learning about governance issues that should be addressed in view of the establishment and exploitation of the linked open data ecosystem.

The interviews will be recorded. Confidentiality of the responses is ensured. The interview protocols will be sent to the interviewees for double-checking.

*Questions in **bold** are to be asked of all interviewees. The answers to the questions in normal script should become evident from the responses; if not, ask these questions specifically. Further instructions to interviewers are in italics.*

Description of the type of organization

Research in advance (see also the LODEPA partner data template) and double check with the interviewee at the beginning of the interview.

What is your role within your organization?

What role does data play for your organization?

In the case of umbrella organizations: ask also with regard to their member organizations (this applies to all questions regarding “your organization”).

Does your organization exchange data with other organizations?

In the case of umbrella organizations: ask also with regard to their members.

- **What data do you receive?**
- **What data do you share with others?**

Does your organization make data available for a broader public?

In the case of umbrella organizations: ask also with regard to their members.

- **What are the target groups**

How does the sharing/exchanging of data across organizational boundaries or with the broader public take place today? And how could it take place in the future?

- Is your organization likely to share some of its data as open data?
- Is your organization likely to rely on other parties to help maintaining the data it requires to carry out its business?
- Is your organization likely to use online communities, crowdsourcing or expert sourcing approaches to help it maintain the data it requires to carry out its business?

What would be the benefits of this new arrangement for your organization?

Have you heard about the Linked Open Data Ecosystem for the Performing Arts?

- **If yes: What do you think about it? What would be the upsides / downsides for your organization? Do you see any particular challenges?**

When you think about the way your organization, its partners and audiences will use, exchange and share data in the future: What extra skills would your staff members require for this?

- **Do you think it would be easy for your staff to acquire the required skill set? Or for your organization to hire the staff with the right skills?**

- What are the skills that are most critical / hardest to acquire?

... **What extra capacities would your organization require?** (e.g. technical, organizational capacities)

... **What are the extra staff skills and organizational capacities required by the organizations you are closely cooperating with?**

Are there any skills or capacities that should rather be built up at the level of the network or the community instead of building them up within every single organization?

- **What skills and capacities would your organization like to provide to the network/community?** To which (type of) organizations specifically? What are their needs?
- **What skills and capacities would your organization like to receive from the network/community?** From which (type of) organization specifically? What are your organization's specific needs?
- What aspects should be given the highest priority when it comes to building up skills/capacities at the network/community level?

When you think about the way your organization will exchange and share data with others in the future, are there any current rules that should be adapted? Are there any new policies or regulations that should be put in place? Any rights to be defined differently? Which ones?

Do you think the culture of working together should be changed? In what ways?

- **What is needed to make this cultural change happen?**
- **Whom do you perceive as the major change agents to make this cultural change happen?** What do they do? How do they proceed?

We have reached the end of the questionnaire. Do you have any further remarks?

Thank you very much for your inputs!

A2. Generation of Sub-categories (Ethical Dimension)

From the text passages associated with a given dimension during the initial categorization (using Atlas.ti), relevant discursive elements were extracted and condensed into sub-categories. The example shown below (ethical dimension, discursive elements from text passages in the literature) is a dimension with comparatively few text passages / sub-categories. Note that sub-categories with discursive elements / text passages from only one source were removed from the further analysis.

Sub-categories / Discursive Elements from Text Passages	Sources
Strike a balance between ensuring the privacy of individuals and utilizing the full potential of the data available	Jensen & Campbell (2019) Jetzek (2017) Kontokosta (2013) Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019) Ubaldi (2013)
Establish when it is appropriate to share what type of data with whom, and who will have authority over which data	Estermann (2020) Jensen & Campbell (2019) Harrison et al. (2012) Ubaldi (2013)
- Make data sharing a new norm in the social license of business to operate	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Establish independent ethics and governance groups to oversee policies and procedures for improving the use of administrative data	Ubaldi (2013)
Hold a public debate to recalibrate society's conventions and increase the moral standards applied to businesses towards privacy and the responsible use of data	Deloitte (2012) Hall et al. (2012)
- Hold wider discussions to identify risks, trade-offs, and the role that different organisations have in ensuring the privacy, security and trust of the individuals and communities they serve	Hall et al. (2012)
- Have all organisations take an active role in engaging citizens and customers in a conversation about the data	Deloitte (2012)
Establish core ethical principles and social values among coders, computers engineers and data scientists	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Establish an ethical protocol at the international level for coders, computer engineers and data scientists which countries and companies adopt and monitor	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Provide training and develop a culture of ethics among coders and data scientists	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
Increase the individual empowerment regarding the (re-)use of personal data	Deloitte (2012)
- Have organisations use the MiData charter to define clearly what data is collected, how it is used and what the benefits are to the individual and to the wider community	Deloitte (2012)
- Have organisations obtain citizens' and customers' informed and explicit consent regarding the use of their personal data	Deloitte (2012)
- Provide the necessary education to ensure that individuals and businesses understand the benefits and challenges of open data (the growing value of open data must go hand in hand with increasing levels of responsibility and governance on its availability and distribution)	Deloitte (2012)

Establish new agile governance models with an increased emphasis on ethics and values to guide technical development, as technological innovation moves faster than institutions	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Ensure that the implementation of a global ecosystem reflects agreed principles of international law and human rights	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Reach a thorough understanding of the implications of potential power imbalances and how they can be mitigated	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Establish a new social contract between companies, governments and citizens where mutual obligations and responsibilities are spelled out	Jensen & Campbell (2019)
- Reach a thorough understanding how companies can resolve potential conflicts of interest that might arise between their public mission of doing good together with the private mission of making money	Jensen & Campbell (2019)

A3. Representation of Sub-categories in a Graph

The image below shows an extract of the graph containing the sub-categories retained, weighted according to the number of sources. For the purpose of the analysis, mind-map like connections were made between the different sub-categories. The extract shows the legal and the ethical aspects extracted from the literature, as well as some of the sub-categories belonging to the political and the organizational dimensions.

A4. Sub-categories retained, organized in four clusters

Cluster	Dimension	Sub-category	Sources / Interviews (Remarks)
Data Sharing	Legal	Create a legal framework that sets clear responsibilities and limitations regarding the sharing of data	(b) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Dawes et al. (2016); van Donge et al. (2022); Harrison et al. (2012); Heimstädt et al. (2014); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Kontokosta (2013); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Legal	Remove the legal barriers that restrict the access to and use of data	(c) Davies (2012); Heimstädt et al. (2014); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Ubaldi (2013)
	Legal	Deal with the impediments caused by intellectual property rights when it comes to the sharing of data and content	(f) Int-1, Int-4, Int-5, Int-8, Int-11, Int-12, Int-13
	Political	Adopt full (open) data policies which foster innovation, ensure privacy protection, and facilitate data sharing and re-use	(d) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); Heimstädt et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Styrin et al. (2017); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Organizational	Ensure full adoption of open data practices by (public sector) organizations	(h) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Bourne et al. (2015); Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); Gama & Loscio (2014); Harrison et al. (2012); Heimstädt et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Martin et al. (2017); Styrin et al. (2017); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Organizational	<i>Have organizations take a pro-active approach towards data management and archiving</i>	(y) Int-1, Int-7, Int-8, Int-9, Int-10, Int-14, Int-15, Int-17 (subsumed under h)
	Organizational	Have data stewards promote the sharing of data across the sector	(e) Int-10, Int-14, Int-15, Int-17
	Organizational	<i>Have an institution coordinate the documenting and archiving of performing arts related material at a national level or at the level of a language region</i>	(i) Int-1, Int-2, Int-7, Int-8 (specific to LODEPA, subsumed under h)
	Organizational Capabilities	Help data owners acquire the skills and capabilities needed to share their data and to adapt their practices	(w) Dawes et al. (2016); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Skills	Educate data providers and data users about the implications of open data	(y) Deloitte (2012); Gupta et al. (2020); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Ubaldi (2013)
Interoperability & Shared Infrastructures	Semantic	Establish standards for harmonizing / integrating different data sources to facilitate information sharing	(p) Bonina & Eaton (2020); van Donge et al. (2022); Gama & Loscio (2014); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Klievink et al. (2018); Kontokosta (2013); Masuzzo & Martens (2015); Ubaldi (2013); Zuiderwijk et al. (2014)
	Semantic	Establish common metadata standards to describe datasets	(o) Bourne et al. (2015); Dawes et al. (2016); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Masuzzo & Martens (2015); Ubaldi (2013)
	Semantic	Develop and use shared ontologies	(a) Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); Estermann (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Kontokosta (2013); Ubaldi (2013); Zuiderwijk et al. (2014)
	Semantic	<i>Establish a shared ontology for the performing arts</i>	(k) Int-2, Int-3, Int-4, Int-7, Int-11, Int-15, Int-16 (specific to LODEPA, subsumed under a)
	Semantic	Provide and use uniform unique identifiers for named entities (authority files, base registers)	(r) Bourne et al. (2015); Estermann (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Kontokosta (2013); Ubaldi (2013); Zuiderwijk et al. (2014)
	Semantic	Establish best practices regarding ontologies and standards	(l) Int-4, Int-7, Int-8, Int-14, Int-16, Int-17
	Technical	Ensure technical interoperability by developing and maintaining open technical and content standards	(s) Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); Gama & Loscio (2014); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Lindman et al. (2016); Masuzzo & Martens (2015); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Technical	Establish a stable data infrastructure that is scalable, available and reliable	(t) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Davies (2012); van Donge et al. (2022); Gama & Loscio (2014); Kontokosta (2013); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Ubaldi (2013)
	Technical	Create and provide common tools and services for working with data	(u) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Bourne et al. (2015); Davies (2012); Gama & Loscio (2014); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Kitsios et al. (2017); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019)
	Technical	<i>Develop and establish common data infrastructures and tools</i>	(u) Int-1, Int-4, Int-5, Int-10, Int-11, Int-14 (subsumed under u)
Organizational Capabilities	Ensure that organizations have access to adequate infrastructures and tools for the management of the data and content they hold	(t) Int-4, Int-5, Int-8, Int-11, Int-14	
Organizational Capabilities	Exploit synergies at the network level to provide access to shared digital infrastructures	(v) Int-2, Int-8, Int-10, Int-14	

Stakeholder Involvement	Ethical	Design the ecosystem in an inclusive manner	(a) Int-3, Int-7, Int-14, Int-16
	Leadership	Get specific change agents to promote the intended change	(v) Int-4, Int-5, Int-6, Int-8, Int-11, Int-12, Int-14, Int-17
	Organizational	Create open data initiatives involving diverse stakeholder groups from the public and private sectors as well as civil society as parts of an ecosystem	(e) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); van Donge et al. (2022); Gama & Loscio (2014); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Kitsios et al. (2017); Klievink et al. (2018); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Martin et al. (2017); Styrin et al. (2017); Ubaldi (2013); Van Schalkwyk et al. (2016); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Organizational	Ensure that all key stakeholder groups are represented within a given data ecosystem	(f) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Bourne et al. (2015); Dawes et al. (2016); Gama & Loscio (2014); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Kitsios et al. (2017); Kontokosta (2013); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Masuzzo & Martens (2015); Styrin et al. (2017); Ubaldi (2013); Van Schalkwyk et al. (2016)
	Organizational	Make sure that central roles are appropriately filled within a given data ecosystem	(g) Bonina & Eaton (2020); Dawes et al. (2016); van Donge et al. (2022); Gupta et al. (2020); Harrison et al. (2012); Klievink et al. (2018); Van Schalkwyk et al. (2016)
	Organizational	Ensure sufficient technical skills among staff members	(b) Int-1, Int-3, Int-4, Int-7, Int-12, Int-14, Int-16
	Organizational Capabilities	Help organizations acquire the necessary technical skills and capabilities to make use of data	(v) Dawes et al. (2016); Deloitte (2012); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Harrison et al. (2012); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019)
	Organizational Capabilities	Make sure that organizations have access to qualified personnel (IT skills and domain expertise) to work on data management tasks	(f) Int-1, Int-2, Int-8, Int-10, Int-11, Int-12, Int-14, Int-16, Int-17
	Organizational Capabilities	<i>Set up training programs to promote skills building</i>	(n) Int-3, Int-6, Int-8, Int-13, Int-14, Int-16, Int-17 <i>(subsumed under f)</i>
	Organizational Capabilities	<i>Foster peer learning</i>	(a) Int-3, Int-6, Int-8, Int-11, Int-13, Int-16 <i>(subsumed under f)</i>
	Organizational Capabilities	<i>Have third parties bring the necessary technical skills to network participants</i>	(p) Int-2, Int-4, Int-7, Int-8, Int-10, Int-11, Int-17 <i>(subsumed under f)</i>
	Skills	Help individuals acquire the specialized technical knowhow required for the publication and use of data	(x) Dawes et al. (2016); Deloitte (2012); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Lnenicka & Komarkova (2019); Ponte (2015); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
	Skills	<i>Researchers need to become data-savvy</i>	(f) Int-3, Int-5, Int-6, Int-8, Int-10, Int-12, Int-14 <i>(specific to LODEPA, subsumed under x)</i>
	Economic Sustainability	Economic	Secure the sustainability of the ecosystem by ensuring that those who make important contributions also experience its benefits
Economic		<i>Secure the necessary resources for data management and digitization</i>	(n) Int-3, Int-6, Int-8, Int-9, Int-11, Int-12, Int-17 <i>(subsumed under l)</i>
Economic		<i>Improve the institutional funding situation of theatres and academic collections</i>	(i) Int-1, Int-7, Int-8, Int-10, Int-14 <i>(specific to LODEPA, subsumed under l)</i>
Economic		Help overcome funding constraints or potential loss of revenue by making initial investments	(m) Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); van Donge et al. (2022); Gupta et al. (2020); Hall et al. (2012); Jetzek (2017); Lindman et al. (2016); Martin et al. (2017); Ubaldi (2013); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
Economic		<i>Secure the necessary project funding</i>	(n) Int-2, Int-3, Int-8, Int-9, Int-10, Int-11, Int-12, Int-13 <i>(subsumed under m)</i>
Economic		Explore and establish new business models around (open) data	(j) Bourne et al. (2015); Dawes et al. (2016); Estermann (2020); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Kitsios et al. (2017); Lindman et al. (2016); Ponte (2015); Ubaldi (2013); Van Schalkwyk et al. (2016); Welle Donker & van Loenen (2017)
Economic		Ensure that open data initiatives are developed from a demand-driven perspective and have a clear value-adding business case	(l) Davies (2012); Dawes et al. (2016); Harrison et al. (2012); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Kontokosta (2013); Martin et al. (2017); Ponte (2015); Ubaldi (2013); Van Schalkwyk et al. (2016)
Economic		Establish a marketplace around data, services and applications	(k) Gama & Loscio (2014); Gupta et al. (2020); Harrison et al. (2012); Immonen et al. (2014); Jensen & Campbell (2019); Jetzek (2017); Martin et al. (2017); Ponte (2015)